

“Masked Emotions”

Measuring Implicit and Explicit Attitudes towards stigmatizing products (dust masks)

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Abstract: New products have an emotional impact on their users and observing bystanders. This is especially true for protective and bodily near products, such as dust masks. Our research started from the hypothesis that reactions to dust masks are generally negative and that people have a spontaneous avoidance reaction. Not only the thoughtful and deliberative reactions, but also the initial unconscious and involuntary reactions, can be very confronting and emotionally challenging towards the stigmatized person. This experimental study aims to test whether the generic distinction between models without dust masks and models with dust masks is sufficient to trigger elementary motor tendencies associated with approach and avoidance, which could serve as an indicator for the product acceptance process. A questionnaire was presented to compare participants' test reactions with their rational and explicit responses. The approach versus avoidance measurements showed a faster approach towards the mask stimuli. Although this result is in contrast with our initial expectations, and to a certain extent with the explicit judgments that were recorded, the results between the different mask-types did provide valuable information. Once we manage to improve our control over the intervening variables, we believe that designers can strongly benefit from this simple and straightforward experimental approach.

Key words: *stigmatizing product, implicit behavior, product acceptance, approach-avoidance*

1. Introduction

Every product is used and perceived in different social environments. Products impact their users but also bystanders who are not using the particular item or service, but inevitably are witnesses to the interaction.

Responses of users and bystanders towards a product can range from very positive to very negative; products can provoke pleasure and admiration, but they can also arouse contempt or disgust.

This is especially true for medical or protective products that are intended to release people from discomforting or unsafe situations. Most of these products are worn or used in close proximity to the human body, defined as bodily near products. Examples include medical products such as prostheses, hearing aids, dental braces, crutches, wheelchairs, knee braces, etc and protective devices such as dust masks, safety helmets and goggles. These products have a more profound impact on their users than products that are designed to express one's

identity. Medical or protective products can reveal a handicap, making their user stand out in undesirable ways. This process can be referred to as a 'stigmatizing impact'.

In recent years the emotional impact of products on the positive side of the acceptance spectrum has been widely studied and described as 'designing pleasurable products' or 'emotional design'. These emotion and pleasure theories include: Don Norman's emotional design model, Patrick Jordan's four pleasures model and the appraisal process as described by Desmet and Hekkert.

The original appraisal theory as defined by Scherer (2001) states that emotions are extracted from our evaluations (appraisals) of events that cause specific reactions in different people [1].

The appraisal process of Desmet (2002) is useful in understanding the process in which emotions towards products are evoked on a cognitive level. In the appraisal process, prior to the emotional reaction, a person evaluates whether an object or event is beneficial or harmful to one or several of his concerns. A pleasant emotion is elicited if the stimulus is assessed as fulfilling one's concerns, and an unpleasant emotion if the stimulus is not beneficial or harmful. A particular emotion towards a product emotion is therefore always a combination of a stimulus and the concerns and expectations of people [2,3].

Norman's (2004) model also offers an explanation of emotion and how it occurs at different cognitive levels. He states that emotion happens at three levels: the visceral, the behavioral, and the reflective. *The visceral level* encompasses the first instinctive reaction to visual and other sensory aspects of a product. It involves the sensory system and has no connection with a reflection of the situation or interaction with the product. The second level of cognitive processing is *the behavioral level*. This level is related to the use of products and covers all interactions between the product and the user. *The reflective level* can be seen as what the person 'thinks' of an object, and is therefore strongly affected by conscious considerations and reflections on past experiences [4].

Jordan (2000) developed a model that distinguishes four 'pleasures' related to the use or possession of a product. *Physio-pleasure* includes pleasures evoked by one or more of the five senses. For example, in the case of protective clothing or accessories, a product will provide people with a physiological need pleasure by protecting them in a potentially dangerous situation. *Socio-pleasure* is the enjoyment derived from relationships with others. Social need pleasures are those that enable us to be comfortable or to avoid discomfort, in these relationships. The desire to avoid stigmatization can be interpreted as a social need pleasure [5]. *Psycho-pleasure* is about people's cognitive and emotional reactions. This could range from issues relating to the cognitive demands of using a product to reactions generated through experiencing the product. *Ideo-pleasures* relate to people's values, tastes and aspirations. On this level issues such as color or styling preferences, as well as values important to the user are addressed [6].

These 3 theoretical models refer to; process steps (Desmet), cognitive feedback levels or loops (Norman), and different psychological affects (Jordan). Process steps, feedback loops and affect levels are different and distinctive dimensions of human functioning in interaction with a given object, product or service. They cannot be classified under a single denominator of 'human emotional impact'. The communality though that can be observed between the three plural impacts in an initiating momentum is one of a reflexive response, starting an appraisal process (Desmet), activating a visceral feedback loop (Norman) and eliciting physio-pleasure (Jordan). Together with or followed by this initial momentum there is a more deliberate response with a reflective content. The question in this experimental research is whether we can observe an unconscious esthetical or emotional

impact that evokes specific initial responses. If so, and if we could determine the dimensions that shape these initial responses, designers could incorporate these elements and possibly elicit a particular emotion or esthetic experience.

We hope that our future insights will provide designers with valuable guidance and present them with the option to design ‘against’ stigma. In the examples below we illustrate possible dimensions that could be valuable for designers. (see Figure 1)

Figure 1. possible dimensions in which a dust-mask could be altered by design.

2. Stigma and products

The concept of stigma has been studied for years within the field of social psychology. Socio-psychological literature shows that stigma and the process of stigmatization are complex phenomena.

Goffman (1963) defined stigma as 'an attribute that is deeply discrediting', and argued that based on the attribute society discriminates against these stigmatized persons. He also argues that visibility is an important factor in the stigma experience. "Having a highly visible stigma causes a person to be 'discredited' instead of merely 'discreditable' as it is in cases in which the stigma can be concealed" [7].

Falk (2001) differentiated between two types of stigmatizing conditions, based on the 'origin' of the stigma. The 'existential stigma' where the person did not cause or has very little control over the stigma (e.g. mental illness, old age, race/ethnicity) or the 'achieved stigma' where a person has earned a stigma because of his or her own conduct and/or because he or she contributed heavily to attaining it (e.g. prisoners, immigrants, homeless persons) [8]. Wearing or using a potentially stigmatizing product charges a person with an achieved stigmatic condition which often results in social exclusion and loss of status.

These definitions share the origin that stigma involves the recognition of some distinguishing characteristic that marks a person as different and leads him to be discredited or devaluated. Importantly, stigma is relationship- and context-specific; it does not reside in the person but in a social context [9].

Rozin, Lowery, and Ebert (1994) suggested that disgust is a common emotion evoked by many stigmas and they conceptualize disgust as a defensive emotion. Things that elicit disgust are perceived as having the potential to contaminate the self physically or socially. A sense of disgust may therefore lead to an immediate desire to avoid the stigmatized [10].

2.1. Dual reactions to stigma

Pryor et al. (2004) indicate that reactions to perceived stigma involve both reflexive and rule-based processes and that each of these processes has a time course. The reflexive process is immediate and, in the case of reactions to stigma, often instinctive, spontaneous and emotional. These spontaneous reactions to stigma are very powerful, but they do not necessarily prevail. Human beings are also capable of more thoughtful, rule-based reactions to stigma. Pryor et al. suggest that people sometimes consider negative reactions to stigma as a form of prejudice. To overcome this initial prejudice reaction, those people might be motivated to compensate this initial reaction by a rule-based and thoughtful reaction that takes more time and presumably more effort to summon.

The reflexive/rule-based theoretical model that Pryor and colleagues have put forward seems useful in the study of reactions to a variety of social stimuli. People may have both reflexive and rule-based reactions to consumer goods, political issues, art, humor, and many other stimuli of social relevance as well as other people [11].

Figure 2. The reflexive/rule-based model of reactions to perceived stigma

The two systems on this figure are assumed to interact dynamically over time. A reflexive reaction is not necessarily replaced by a later rule-based reaction. Pryor et al. also indicate that the reflexive processes may reemerge during subsequent encounters if the stigmatizing attribute is re-experienced or if one is reminded of the stigma [12].

2.2. Behavioral responses to stigma

There is a consensus within socio-psychological literature that avoidance seems to be a defining and immediate reaction to stigma. People act as if physical contact or even proximity to the stigmatized can result in some form of contamination. Although socio-psychological literature indicates that the emotional and behavioral responses to stigma are very complex, most researchers agree that a basic underlying dimension of both emotions and behaviors is one of approach and avoidance [13-19]. Or as Pryor et al. states it: “An intimate psychological linkage between positive–negative feelings and approach–avoidance tendencies.” [20].

From the perspective of the designer, it would be challenging to gain more insight in the emotional impact and the dimensions that shape the product acceptance process by observing, measuring and interpreting people’s behavioral responses, and their approach and avoidance like tendencies. Although this research primarily focuses on the implicit or reflexive response, an explicit or reflective questionnaire is added to the procedure. By comparing the results on both tasks we can verify whether the implicit and explicit responses are consistent and/or whether they diverge on this socially sensitive issue.

3. Method

Approach and avoidance-like experiments have been widely used and validated in socio-psychological research. In 1996, Chen and Bargh asked participants to evaluate words presented on a computer screen as either “good” or “bad” by pushing or pulling a lever. Their results illustrated that the perception of a stimulus as positive or negative primes or facilitates approach or avoidance motor behavior, respectively [21].

We selected the Approach and Avoidance Motor Behavior experiment as described by Paladino and Castelli (2009) [22]. Their work relies strongly on previous studies but differentiates in several aspects. Whereas previous studies used (out)groups that were characterized by highly stigmatizing features, such as child molesters or HIV-infected individuals, their research includes a wide range of groups that do not involve a personal threat. (e.g., age and political groups). In contrast to other research this procedure also considers the responses to ingroup members; people without masks in our study.

Within this experimental research the dependent variable is the reaction time. The independent variables are type of movement (approach versus avoidance movement) towards pictures of people with vs. without masks and varying the type of masks confronting competent, warmth and neutral masks. All these variables were manipulated within-participants. Only the order in which participants had to respond to the different mask types and the first response they had to give to classify masks was counterbalanced between participants.

In this study we used dust masks as evokers/carriers of stigma.

4. Experiment

4.1. Pre-test to select evocative stimuli

The dust masks for this experiment were selected on the basis of a pre-test. We initially searched for dimensions that could be useful in classifying the existing dust masks that are on the market. In our pre-test we used the universal dimensions of social cognition, as described by Fiske and colleagues (2002, 2007): Warmth and Competence. Fiske states that people who are perceived as warm and competent elicit uniformly positive emotions and behavior. On the other hand, stigmatized groups tend to be negatively stereotyped on the dimensions of competence and/or warmth in most cultures. Stereotyping people along these two dimensions may be functional; in order to survive, people need to know who is friend or foe (warmth) and who can enact on these basic benevolent or hostile intentions (competence) [23].

It would be interesting to find out whether these two dimensions facilitate the acceptance of dust masks if they change the perception of the person that is wearing them in terms of ‘competence’ or ‘warmth’ in comparison to a selection of reference masks. Therefore, we selected three different types of masks that were thought to represent one of these dimensions. The so-called competence masks were dust masks used in different professions and in sports. The reference masks were neutral, white dust masks, which are the most commonly used on the market. The warmth masks were personalized and colorful masks that were made especially for this experiment. In order to select those masks that best represented their category a pre-test was conducted with 16 participants, of which 9 males and 7 females. Participants’ age ranged from 20 to 35 years old ($M = 23$, $SD = 2.76$). All participants had the Italian nationality and were Italian native speakers. In the pre-test they were asked to rate 44 pictures of people with dust masks on 7 dimensions, each on a 7-point scale. Three dimensions were related to warmth (friendly, well-intending, sociable), three to competence (capable, competent, efficient), and one to beauty (attractive). On the basis of these judgments we selected the three masks that best represented their

category and conducted separate one-way ANOVA's on competence, warmth, and attractiveness judgments comparing these judgments for the different types of masks.

Testing for differences on the competence dimension between mask type results showed a significant main effect $F(2, 30) = 4.49, p < .05$. In contrast with our hypothesis the images we labeled as competence masks scored low on competence traits, i.e. people classified people that were wearing reference and warmth masks, respectively, as more competent and efficient than the actual competence masks (comparing means: REFmasks $M = 4.33, SD = 1.39$; Wmasks $M = 4.12, SD = 1.34$; C masks $M = 3.61, SD = 1.21$). The judgments on the warmth dimension also showed a significant main effect, $F(2, 30) = 33.93, p < .001$, revealing that perceived warmth was indeed higher for people who wore warmth masks. Mean comparison tells us that warmth masks were perceived as warmer and more friendly ($M = 4.81, SD = 1.30$) compared to reference ($M = 3.79, SD = 1.14$) and competence masks ($M = 2.75, SD = 0.85$).

Finally, testing for differences between the mask on attractiveness, a significant main effect emerged, $F(2, 30) = 8.54, p < .001$, showing that people who wore both warmth or reference masks were seen as more attractive ($M = 3.07, SD = 1.50$ and $M = 2.75, SD = 1.10$ for warmth and reference masks respectively) than the competence masks ($M = 1.92, SD = 0.67$).

Overall, the pre-test data showed that masks that are mainly used in a professional environment do not convey competence on the persons who are wearing them, while personalizing a mask significantly increases the level of warmth the person wearing the mask is thought to have. These differences are important to bear in mind when interpreting the results of the main study.

4.2. Experimental setup

The selected stimuli were presented on a computer screen and the participants' speed of approach-like and avoidance-like movements toward and away from models with no masks and models with masks were compared. At the end of the experiment the same participants were asked to fill out a questionnaire with the intent to compare their implicit (reflexive) and spontaneous reactions with their rational (reflective) and explicit answers. This study aims to test whether the generic distinction between models without dust masks and models with dust masks is sufficient to trigger elementary motor tendencies associated with approach and avoidance.

Participants.

This research was conducted on a sample of 48 students and former students at the University of Padova, of which 20 males and 28 females. Participants' age ranged from 19 to 32 years old ($M = 21, SD = 2.81$). All participants had the Italian nationality and all but one were Italian native speakers. Data from this latter participant were excluded from the analysis due to the high number of mistakes that were made (i.e., in one of the three blocks, responses did not match the instructions). All students participated voluntarily.

Materials.

Three images depicting persons wearing a mask were selected within each category that was created (warmth, competence, reference). In addition, a single image of a person without a mask was selected as well. Each of the 4 models (2 females and 2 males) was seen wearing all of the masks. Thus, participants saw 10 different images of each of the 4 models, creating a total of 40 stimuli.

Figure 3. An overview of all 40 stimuli – Four models and 4 conditions

Images were presented on a computer screen, which was situated at a distance of approximately 50 centimeters from the person. We provided the modified keyboard already used in other approach-avoidance tasks [21,23]. This is a standard keyboard from which all buttons have been removed and replaced by three bigger wooden buttons: an upper (approach), a central and a lower one (avoidance). The upper one was colored in red and the lower one in green, while the central one had no color. The keyboard was displayed in a vertical position and adjusted to the right or to the left according to the participant's dominant hand (see Figure 4). Given the position of the keyboard, each participant had to respond by moving their arm toward (approach-like movement) or away from (avoidance-like movement) the stimulus that was presented on the computer screen when pressing the forward and backward keys, respectively.

Figure 4. the experimental setup

Procedure.

Implicit judgments. Participants were divided into two conditions: 24 followed the instructions of the mask approach condition while the remaining 24 conducted the experiment in the no-mask approach condition. In the **mask approach** condition, participants' first task was to press the approach button for images of models wearing a mask, whereas in the **no-mask approach** condition, their first task consisted in pressing the approach button for images of models without a mask. In this way, participants' first response instructions were counterbalanced, even though all participants had to respond to all stimuli both using an approach and an avoidance-like movement. Every response trial was structured as follows: participants were requested to press the red (approach) or green (avoidance) button for mask or no-mask images, depending on condition. Immediately after giving their response they had to press the central button. When they did this correctly, they heard a beep that signaled that the next image was about to appear. Participants were asked to wait for the new image holding their hand above the central button. Participants were required to be as quick as possible in giving responses and to make as little mistakes as possible.

The complete task consisted of 3 blocks. In each block participants were confronted with one of the three mask types: warmth masks, competence masks, and reference masks. Even though every participant responded to each mask type in different blocks, the order in which the various categories of masks appeared was counterbalanced between participants. See Figure 5 for an overview of the experimental set-up.

Every single block was structured in 4 phases that were presented as follows: first the computer program displayed a trial sequence of 4 images that aimed to verify whether the person understood the specific task instructions correctly. Immediately following this training phase participants saw all the stimuli responding to the specific instructions. The third phase was again a training phase in which, the response instructions were reversed. For example, if a participant had pressed the red button for mask images and the green button for no-mask images, he or she would now have to press the green one for mask images and the red one for no-mask images or vice versa. While this third phase only consisted of 4 images, it was followed by the fourth phase in which participants responded to all the stimuli with the new instructions.

In each block, 24 stimuli were presented twice in a random order, once with one pair of instructions and once with reversed instructions. Hence, the complete task made up of 3 blocks comprised 144 trials.

		6 conditions					
		Starting with warmth		Starting with competence		Starting with reference	
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Experiment	Starting with No Mask approach ↓	W	W	C	C	R	R
		R	C	R	W	W	C
		C	R	W	R	C	W
	24 participants	4	4	4	4	4	4
Starting with Mask approach ↓	W	W	C	C	R	R	
	R	C	R	W	W	C	
	C	R	W	R	C	W	
	24 participants	4	4	4	4	4	4
		Total of 48 participants					

Figure 5. overview of the division between participants and experimental conditions

Explicit judgments. At the end of the computer task, participants were invited to fill in a questionnaire, while they were shown 4 images, one by one. These images pictured all 4 models: three of them were wearing masks and one was barefaced. The models that were wearing masks all belonged to the same mask type and corresponded to the masks participants saw in the first block of the computer task. The implicit judgments from the first block are more genuine and are not comparative, being free from any habituation to the task or influence of seeing other types of masks in previous blocks. Therefore, we only confronted the implicit judgments of the first task with the explicit judgments at the end of the questionnaire. The masks were presented in a fixed order but the model that was wearing them was randomized. The fourth target was always the one wearing no mask. As such, each participant judged each model once and each of three masks of a single category (i.e., warmth or competence or reference).

In the first question of the questionnaire, we asked participants to pretend they were actually meeting the person pictured for the first time, exactly the way he/she appeared. They had to imagine this for each target and answer four questions about general liking (e.g., How much do you like this person? How much would you like to meet this person?). All ratings were made on 7-point Likert type scales ranging from 1 (not at all) to 7 (very much).

4.3. Results

Implicit judgments.

Given the presence of order effects and the inevitable comparative nature of the implicit judgments that were recorded after the first phase, only the analysis of the reaction times of the first phase that compares the influence of mask type between participants is reported. Response latencies of 47 participants were taken into consideration, excluding very slow (slower than or exceeding 3,000 ms) and very fast reaction times (faster than or below 300 ms). These outliers were processed as errors together with the incorrect responses and made up 2.6% of the total amount of responses. The remaining responses were log-transformed and analyzed in a 2 (Target: mask vs. no-mask images) x 2 (Behavioral response: approach vs. avoidance) x 2 (First response: no-mask approach vs. mask approach) x 3 (Mask type: warmth vs. competence vs. reference) mixed ANOVA of which the first two factors were measured within-participants and the latter two between-participants. From this analysis a main effect of Behavioral response emerged, $F(1, 41) = 9.86, p < .05$ showing that participants were generally faster at approaching rather than avoiding the different targets. In addition, the two-way interaction between participants' Behavioral response and Target resulted to be significant, $F(1, 41) = 8.84, p < .05$. Mean comparisons showed that approach movements were performed faster towards mask images ($INV LN = 757.48$) compared to avoidance movements ($INV LN = 780.55$), while the reverse was true for the no-mask images ($INV LN = 820.57$ and $INV LN = 749.95$ for approach and avoidance reactions respectively). Importantly, these effects were qualified by the three-way interaction between Target, Behavioral response and Mask type that showed to be marginally significant, $F(2, 41) = 2.53, p = .092$. In order to get a better understanding of this interaction separate 2 (target: mask vs. no-mask images) x 2 (behavioral response: approach vs. avoidance) within subjects ANOVA's were calculated for each mask type (warmth, competence and reference).

For the "warmth" masks, apart from a significant main effect of participants' Behavioral response, no other significant effects emerged ($F < 1$). For these masks there was no statistically relevant difference in how fast masks and bare faces were approached or avoided.

For the “competence” masks, we obtained a significant interaction effect, $F(1, 14) = 10.18, p < .05$, showing that competence masks were approached faster ($M = 735.94$ ms) than avoided ($M = 789.81$ ms), while the reverse happened for the no-mask images ($M = 822.9$ ms and $M = 753.49$ for approach and avoidance reactions respectively).

Also the analysis on the reactions to the “reference” masks, showed a significant interaction effect, $F(1, 13) = 7.99, p < .05$, between target and behavioral responses. Participants responded faster approaching ($M = 764.63$ ms) than avoiding ($M = 873.68$ ms) reference masks, while the reverse happened for the correspondent bare faces ($M = 882.18$ and $M = 759.92$ for approach and avoidance movements respectively).

Figure 6. Between participant comparisons by mask type (only first block) - Interaction of 3 factors: approach/avoid, mask/no mask and mask type (from left to right: warmth, competence, reference)

Explicit judgments

Liking. The four first questions of the questionnaire all reflected general liking and were aggregated in a single index ($\alpha = .72$) that was calculated separately for the models with mask and compared with the barefaced model. These means were analyzed in a 2 (Target: mask vs. no-mask) x 3 (Mask type: warmth vs. competence vs. reference) mixed ANOVA of which the first factor was calculated within-participants and the second one between-participants. Results showed to be non-significant ($F < 1$) thus liking was not qualified by any type of mask. Still, the depicted means in Figure 7 shows that participants showed a tendency to like the warm masks slightly more compared to the bare faces. This difference, however, was only marginally significant ($p = .11$). Moreover, the mean judgment on liking was the highest ($M = 3.7$) for warmth masks. Clearly no differences emerged for competence and reference masks.

Figure 7. Explicit liking judgments in function of the target and the type of mask (non significant interaction).

Looking at the ANOVA calculated on the means of judgments on professionalism (specialist, professional, scientist, $\alpha = .62$) we found a significant main effect of target, $F(1, 44) = 12.11, p < .01$, which states that overall masked persons were judged as more professional ($M = 3.82$) than the bare faces ($M = 3.16$). Moreover, a significant interaction effect emerged between target and mask type, $F(2, 44) = 3.29, p < .05$, indicating that competence masks were seen as the most professional among the mask types ($M = 4.07$), and in comparison to the corresponding no-mask images ($M = 2.73$) (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Professionalism means of interaction between type of mask and mask_nomask (significant $p < .05$)

4.4. Discussion

Following the implicit data masks don't seem to be stigmatizing, indeed reaction times were faster to approach the mask stimuli. This result is however in contrast with our expectations and to a certain extent also with the explicit judgments given by participants. Indeed, the least liked masks implicitly tend to be the most liked ones explicitly.

An alternative explanation could be formulated, however, that directly follows the way in which the experiment was set up. People had to decide whether something was present (mask) or not. Translating participants' task in these terms could mean that people were faster in approaching masks because it is easier to point at something (making a forward movement) present than to point at something absent. Following this explanation, it could indeed be that also the implicit measure shows that people liked the warmth masks better, because this facilitation effect was absent for the warmth masks. Interpreting the data from this perspective, we could suggest that these are the masks that are most likely ignored on the face of a person. In any case more research is needed to deal with this alternative explanation. In a new experiment we are changing the original setup asking participants for example to categorize people with glasses or a mask.

5. Conclusions

Our literature research has indicated that stigma theory and experimental techniques within the socio-psychological literature can be inspirational to the field of design research. Understanding and interpreting basic behavioral tendencies towards potentially stigmatizing products in a first implicit confrontation as well as the more deliberate and thoughtful responses can be a basis for acceptance related issues. Providing the designer with simple and straightforward research tools to predict and anticipate both these reactions remains the prime objective of our research. At the same time these experiments can shed light on the dimensions that impact the product acceptance process.

The methodology that was used in this study is simple and cost efficient. The approach/avoidance reactions towards mask and no-mask stimuli, clearly followed interpretable patterns and varied in function of the dimensions of interest. It would therefore be beneficial to replicate this study with stimuli that have a product in or around the face in both conditions. (e.g. glasses, hat, scarf). At the same time, it is our aim to reduce the esthetical variability between the mask categories and attempt to describe the design implications more clearly in future research. When we manage to improve our control over the intervening variables and introduce a way to visualize the results in a designer oriented way, we believe that designers can strongly benefit from this experimental approach.

However, in order to make a substantial step forward, we will have to further improve our understanding of the product acceptance process. Not only a reflexive/reflective 'feedback loop' (Pryor; Norman) is key in human interaction with products. Also the emotion evoking 'evaluation process' (Desmet), as well as the human 'behavioral functions' that are invested in the interaction, are vital to this acceptance process. To each of these three human interaction dimensions, we can allocate physiological, cognitive, emotional and behavioral aspects. In order to add value to the design context, we will need a more integral and consistent theoretical model to explain the aggregate impact on product acceptance, in this case stigma. It will allow product designers to predict not only the first implicit response of a product user or a bystander, but also to explain enduring attitudes towards new products.

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